

Designing of Key Performance Indicators based on Sustainability Balanced Scorecard in Tourism and Hospitality Sector

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Abstract

Balanced Scorecard has attracted considerable interest from practitioners and experts across diverse sectors. It helps to categorise quantifiable objectives of an organisation generally into four perspectives: financial (economic), customer (recipient of final product or service outcome), internal business processes and learning and growth perspectives respectively. The paper aims to design Key Performance Indications based on Sustainability Balanced Scorecard in Tourism and Hospitality Sector in the emerging economies which are becoming the major centre for tourist attraction. The study aims to provide valuable input in designing sustainability balanced scorecard in the context of hospitality and tourism industry an area that has been less researched.

Keywords: Sustainability Balanced Scorecard, perspectives, key performance indicators, Hospitality industry, tourism industry

1. Introduction

Balanced Scorecard is a performance measurement tool has gained considerable importance since its induction by Kaplan and Norton in 1992. BSC helps to categorise quantifiable performance indicators of an organisation generally into four perspectives: financial (economic), customer (recipient of final product or service outcome), internal business processes and learning and growth perspectives respectively (Biswas, 2021). Due to its versatility and convenience it can be applied to a wide array of industrial and service sectors (Alvarez et.al, 2018; Catuogno et al., 2017). The economic impact of hospitality and tourism industry on a country's GDP has increased significantly in the last few years. The industry contributed an overall of 10.3% to global GDP in 2019 (WTTC, 2020). Emerging economies such as India has witnessed unprecedented growth in travel and tourism industry contributing to 256 billion dollars to the country's GDP, welcoming over 9 million foreign tourists, generating huge foreign exchange earnings of over \$27 billion in the year 2023-2024 (Keelery, 2025). Despite witnessing a severe brunt by the coronavirus pandemic where the overall contribution of the industry was adversely impacted by up to about 80% during 2020-

2021 (OECD, 2020), the industry has witnessed unprecedented growth post pandemic. The perspectives of the Balanced Scorecard are not mutually exclusive. Owing to the credibility of the concept for evaluating the strategic plan its application in the Tourism and Hospitality industry cannot be undermined. The study aims to consider the strategy for the development of BSC in the sector in the context of emerging economies witnessing unprecedented tourist attraction of both domestic and foreign tourists with a continued huge escalation in the contribution of the tourism and Hospitality industry towards the GDP. The paper aims to develop a Balanced and Sustainable performance measurement tool for Tourism and hospitality organisations in emerging market economies who are facing numerous and uncontrollable challenges in a highly competitive global market. As this industry caters to the needs of both domestic and foreign tourists the charges are highly dependent on International Market Parameters such as the foreign exchange rate, charges of international flights and freight, Geopolitical relations across regions and countries and more. Despite the multidimensional nature of organisational performance researchers have mostly focused on the lagged indicators of organisational performance such as the lagged financial indicators rather than focusing on the leading indicators of measurement (Fatima & Elbanna, 2020; Bento et al., 2017). Hence a more multidimensional approach to measure organisational performance is needed which has been solved by the emergence and induction of the balanced scorecard however the balanced scorecard has evolved overtime and this study has incorporated another dimension – the sustainability perspective in balanced scorecard (Biswas, 2021). Balanced Score card is multidimensional incorporating both financial and non-financial indicators having both leading and lagging indicators with short as well as long term key performance measures. Despite the increasing importance of the implication of BSC across diverse sectors such as banking, public sector undertakings, health care as well as small scale industries the application of this multi -criteria tool in hospitality and tourism industry has been less explored (Fatima & Elbanna, 2020).

Performance measurement is vital to an organisation as it provides a direction to management with regard to decision making through review of past performance, evaluation of the present functioning and analysing the future strategies for successful operation of the organisation towards fulfilment of the strategic goals (Gawankar et. Al., 2015).

Some of the basic concepts to analyze the need for performance measurement are stated in the Table 1.

Table 1

SL. NO.	Basic concepts to analyze the need for performance measurement
1.	Something that cannot be measured hence cannot be understood and vice versa
2.	Something that cannot be understood hence cannot be controlled
3.	Having controllability is vital to improvement and improvisation
4.	The intention to measure a performance is important
5.	Success can be distinguished from failure only through performance measurement of the resultant outcome – When the expected or the target exceeds actual measures of performance and vice versa based on the situation success and failure can be distinguished
6.	Success should be visible through the resultant outcome for its proper rewarding
7.	Due to lack of proper performance measurement outcome often failures / unsuccessful outcomes are rewarded
8.	A success is only sustainable only if it is duly Identified, measured and recognised
9.	The resultant outcome either a success or failure should be duly assessed and evaluated for corrective measures, Learning and growth
10.	In the aftermath of failure, assessment and evaluation of the causes of failure is integral to performance measurement for improved performance, rectification of errors and mistakes and optimization of resource usage
11.	The efficiency ratio, effectiveness ratio, the output and the outcome should be understood to assess the real cost both implicit and explicit
12.	Ascertainment of actual of production is important in managerial decision making with regard to make or buy decisions
13.	Similarly, ascertainment of the full cost or real cost including both the implicit and the explicit cost of production or purchase is integral to get the best value for money and for optimization of resources. Consideration of opportunity cost will enable an organisation to take right decisions between make and buy options or during contracting options
14.	Both internal and external stakeholders are interested in the results so communication of the resultant outcome while evaluating the best value for

	money alternatives to the stakeholders will facilitate organisational performance and improve stakeholders' confidence in the organisation
15.	Choosing the most effective value for money alternative through objective method in order to achieve the organisational objectives. Subjective measures / Random measures of evaluation of alternative proposals are highly questionable
16.	Performance outcome must be measured in comparison to the established industry standards or that of against the performance of powerful competitors within the same industry. Measuring performance outcome is often a comparative analysis. Hence the performance outcome is expected to be at par or above the established industry standard
17.	Assessing and understanding the satisfaction level of the stakeholders based on their interest (Subjects and crowd) and the power they exercise (Players and context setters) in the organisation is important to performance measurement. Effective change management system should be adopted by every organisation

Performance measurement Using the application of balanced scorecard

Excessive reliance exclusively on financial performance measures could jeopardise the competitive edge of organisations as financial indicators are outcome measures and lagged indicators which do not reflect the future performance and value creation. Hence to overcome the weakness of reliance on only financial measures Kaplan and Norton inducted the customer, suppliers, employees, process, technology, learning and innovation outcomes in the quadrant of balanced scorecard. The balanced scorecard is a balanced approach that incorporates different measures with different perspectives tied together to give a holistic view of the organisation.

- Balance between financial and non - financial indicators

This paper tries to incorporate the ways in which balanced scorecard can realise the sustainability objectives by designing of the sustainability balance scorecard considering sustainability as the need of the hour. Researchers have actively tried to explore ways in which organizations can utilize Balanced Scorecards to realize their sustainability objectives which has paved the way for a new stream of perspectives – sustainability BSC. Hence sustainability can be incorporated in the balanced scorecard either as a part of the existing perspectives or as an extended dimension all together. The sustainability dimension in BSC

integrates environmental and social perspectives (Hansen and Schaltegger, 2018; Fatima & Elbanna, 2020; Biswas, 2021). Owing to the nature of tourism and hospitality industry, its intangible assets and its extensive focus on human resources, labour intensive nature, inconsistency in services and the nature of activities necessitates the application of a comprehensive performance measurement system to measure both the financial performance and employee performance as well as the satisfaction level of customers.

To ensure revamping, betterment, sustenance and primary stakeholders' satisfaction (tourists) in the Tourism and hospitality industry a multidimensional and sustainable performance measurement system should be conceptualised, designed and implemented.

The scope of tourism and hospitality industry

Tourism and hospitality industry can be broadly classified into 4 subsets accommodation, food and beverage, transportation, activities and attractions. Accommodation is the most crucial component of this industry which extends from hotels, resorts to vacation rentals where the service providers are responsible for providing visitors with a comfortable and safe stay during their trip.

The second subset of this industry is food and beverage which includes restaurants, cafes, clubs, eateries, bars that provide food and beverage to the visitors.

The third component is transportation which includes all the modes of transportation Such as airlines, buses, taxis, rental cars to help visitors get from one place to the other during the trip.

The fourth component of tourism and hospitality is activities and attractions which aim to provide visitors with unique experiences combined with adventure, cultural immersions, natural wonders to provide them with lifetime of memorable and aesthetic experience. It includes visits to theme parks, adventure sports, tours. The four components of this industry work together seamlessly to provide travellers with memorable experiences. These four segments are intertwined, a poor performance in one segment can deter the overall customer experience hence all the segments require equal importance and weightage.

2.1. BSC performance perspectives

Based on the organisational characteristics, mission and objectives every organisation may identify different balanced scorecard perspectives to achieve the best reflection of its strategies.

Organisations may customise and improvise the perspectives based on the situations and needs (Alvarez et.al, 2018). Most of the organisations preferred to apply the four traditional

BSC perspectives (Aujirapongpan et al. 2019; Behrouzi, et al. 2014; Alvarez et.al, 2018). The principal concern of Tourism and hospitality organisations should be customers and providing services based on their mission and goals. The BSC provides a framework for reporting about performance, aligns strategic direction with internal processes and inculcates the need for continuous quality improvement. Assessing the performance outcome of each individual perspective of the balanced scorecard is vital as well as the aggregated BSC may be applied to obtain an overall understanding about the performance outcome of the organisation (Aujirapongpan et al. 2020).

Traditional Perspectives:

Customer perspective: The term customer means end users or end consumers or buyers or beneficiary of the final Product and service outcome. In the context of Tourism and hospitality industry customers mean visitors, tourists, Travellers or guests who are the recipients of Tourism and hospitality services. Tourism and hospitality institutions have to devote greatest efforts to this perspective since they are the ultimate recipients of the actions of improvement. The customer perspective is an illustrative concept and includes several parameters of performance measurement aimed to assess and improve the perceived value of customers with regard to services received, enhanced customer safety, Satisfaction and holistic experience (Kaplan & Norton 1996, 2001; Alvarez et.al, 2018; Catuogno et al., 2017; Trotta et al., 2013; Aujirapongpan et al. 2020). Thus customer perspective forms one of the basic pillars for tourism and hospitality industry. This industry has witnessed massive evolution over the years with incorporation of sustainability factors and more emphasis on customer retention perspective. The fast-changing business environment with business model innovation emphasise the importance of continuous change management and improved value creation in industry such as tourism and hospitality the revenue creation of which are often jeopardised due to even minor changes in domestic and international market (Biswas, 2023).

Financial perspective: The financial perspective is an illustrative concept and includes several parameters of performance measurement. The financial perspective focuses on return and sustained revenue generation keeping in mind the investors interest who are the major stakeholders of the organisation. Performance measurement from the perspective of finance is usually measured in quantitative terms but it is usually a lagging indicator where the deviation between the actual and the expected or the actual and the standard is often generically considered as either favourable or adverse based on output maximisation or input minimization objective. This perspective should follow the customers' perspective in the

context of Tourism and hospitality industry (Kaplan & Norton, 2001; Trotta et al., 2013; Catuogno et al., 2017; Biswas, 2021).

Internal process perspective: The Internal process perspective includes several parameters of performance measurement. It aims to incorporate the focal points of customer satisfaction in the internal processes and their subsequent refinement, revamping of internal processes to provide enhanced and sustained customer (tourist) satisfaction. The measurement and assessment of competency, efficacy, optimization of resource usage and effectiveness in the processes and more falls within its purview. It aims at producing and delivering the value proposition for customers and improving processes and decreasing costs for the efficiency of financial perspective (Biswas, 2021). This re-emphasizes on the point that the perspectives are not mutually exclusive. The customer perspective is followed by the internal business process perspective where the focal point is organisations' adherence to streamlined process for an efficient and effective service delivery. It facilitates both direct and indirect improvement of performance of various perspectives including financial social and environment.

Learning and growth perspective: Since human resource is the heart of tourism and hospitality industry and its utmost dependence on its staff being its labour-intensive nature and customization of services to be provided to different customers emphasises on focus on the learning and growth perspective. The Learning and Growth perspective includes several parameters of performance measurement aimed to assess the steps to enhance involvement of human resources in the organisation to facilitate higher efficiency, effective communication superior quality and sustained innovation, enhanced and wilful participation of staff at both strategic and functional levels for undertaking research, nurturing of innovative ideas for growth and competence (Kaplan & Norton 1996, 2001; Catuogno et al., 2017; Trotta et al., 2013; Aujirapongpan et al. 2020). This industry sustains on feedback and how the feedback can be turned into opportunity and scope for improvement relies on how this perspective can be nurtured.

Sustainability perspective of the balanced scorecard

The hospitality and tourism industry is actively adopting the concept of sustainability (Vila et al., 2010) and the researchers are looking keenly into measuring sustainable tourism. The non-financial perspectives of the balanced scorecard weighs equally important as the financial perspective as customer satisfaction and customer retention is the key to success in hospitality and tourism industry. Past studies have proposed the development of sustainability balanced scorecard for hospitality and tourism industry that caters to the industry specific

needs through utilising the strategic stakeholder theory (Fatima and Elbanna, 2020). The strategic stakeholder theory recognises the importance of stakeholders and emphasises on providing utmost satisfaction to them leading to better product and service relationships, improved stakeholder confidence and organisational performance. While designing the sustainability balanced scorecard an organisation is driven by the need to attain competitive advantage hence social and environmental perspectives should coexist with financial perspectives (Hansen and Schaltegger, 2018). The sustainability balanced scorecard aims to realise the objective of meeting societal goals, preservation of the environment along with improved profits for organisational sustenance. The sustainability balance scorecard broadly incorporates all the three perspectives financial, social and environmental as three pillars to be an appropriate performance measurement tool in the hospitality and tourism industry. Since the core part of this industry is service provision by the employees for the customers hence the traditional perspectives of the balanced scorecard that is the customer perspective, internal business process and the learning and growth perspectives serves as the pillars of SBSC.

2.2. Indicators and goals of the perspective's objectives:

Monitoring of the objectives of different perspectives can be facilitated through the development/designing of relevant indicators which shall help to study results analytically and objectively. The performance management indicators should be able to provide a concrete and unambiguous understanding of the contribution of each initiative in the strategic plan within a given timeframe.

Table I

BSC perspectives Objectives - Key performance indicators – brief generalised summary with reference to Tourism and hospitality industry (Catuogno et al., 2017; Trotta et al., 2013; Aujirapongpan et al. 2020; Biwas, 2021)

BSC Perspectives	Perspective Objectives	Key Performance Indicators
Customers (Tourists, visitors, guests)	CO ₁ – Enhancement of customer satisfaction and perceived value of services received by Customers across all the four segments food, accommodation, transportation and activities CO ₂ – Sustained Improvement of image brand value and holistic experience CO ₃ – Ensuring utmost safety and security to guests and nullify any vulnerability if any CO ₄ – Provide customers with cross subsidisation of services and a lifetime of memorable experience	CPI ₁ - Rate of customer complaints CPI ₂ - Percentage of customer satisfaction CPI ₃ – Perceived Value of Customers for services received in a scale of 1-5 CPI ₄ – Time taken to resolve customer issues CPI ₅ – Bundling of services provided to customers CPI ₆ – Customer feedback on all categories of services provided measured on a quantitative scale
Financial	FO ₁ - Compliance with the strategic budget FO ₂ - Generation of sufficient self-financing	FPI ₁ - Ratio of total revenue to total costs

	<p>to meet the Organisational objectives</p> <p>FO₃ - Generation of admissible profit</p> <p>FO₄ - Financially sustain mission and vision of the organisation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Optimum capital structure attainment to maximise the value of the farm • Respect budget constraints • Cost containment • Fund rising • Increase in customers' base <p>FO₅- Optimise operating and other administrative costs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capture new avenues • Achieve financial balance by effective cost-revenue management 	<p>FPI₂ – Percentage of service cost / Total cost</p> <p>FPI₃ - Percentage of Operating cost / Total cost</p> <p>FPI₄ - Percentage of personnel cost / Total cost</p> <p>FPI₅ - Percentage of compliance cost (taxes, legal costs etc.) / Total cost</p> <p>FPI₆ – Percentage of training costs to total costs / Total cost</p> <p>FPI₇- Percentage of sales and administration overhead to total cost</p>
Internal Process	<p>IPO₁ - To improve the organisational set up</p> <p>IPO₂ - Maximise customers' Satisfaction</p> <p>IPO₃ - Reduction of Complaints rate to negligible percentage</p> <p>IPO₄ - To improve the Service and process efficiency</p> <p>IPO₅ - To improve the quality, experience exposure and efficacy of the all the four segments of tourism and hospitality</p> <p>IPO₆ - Offer specialised treatment and services</p>	<p>IPI₁ - Average length of stay</p> <p>IPI₂ - Room turnover</p> <p>IPI₃ - Room occupancy</p> <p>IPI₄ – Revisit and rebooking rate</p> <p>IPI₅ – Number and tenure of Sharing of Intellectual property agreements Such as licencing And franchising with other Players in the domestic and international market of tourism and hospitality</p> <p>IPI₆ – Number of intellectual properties such as patents filed Within the last 10 years</p> <p>IP₇ – Ratio of any claim for damages to the customers to total revenue or earnings after tax</p>
Learning and Growth	<p>LGO₁ - To motivate the Tourism and hospitality staff, allied professionals, associated practitioners</p> <p>LGO₂ - To increase the training/exposure of functional and strategic personnel</p> <p>LGO₃ - Enhancement of staff competence</p> <p>LGO₄ - Facilitation of two-way internal communication</p> <p>LGO₅ – Facilitation of scope of continuous innovation to provide improved services through continuous learning by virtue of conducting human resource management programmes from time to time</p>	<p>LGPI₁ – Staff satisfaction rate (Across all the four segments separately)</p> <p>LGPI₂ - Staff turnover rate (Across all the four segments separately)</p> <p>LGPI₃ – Number of orientation programmes conducted for staff during the financial year</p> <p>LGPI₄ – Number disruptive business models in this industry such as subscription model, Cross subsidisation model, free model or service ecosystem model and more</p>

3. Discussion and Conclusion

This industry thrives on the sentiment and the comfort and composure they can provide to the customers. The empirical researches on BSC adoption and implementation have considerably

changed with the change of industry needs. Table II highlights the possible ways in which the SBSC can assist to meet existing Tourism and hospitality challenges.

Orientation sessions need to be held with the Tourism and hospitality staff and professionals to enlighten them about the meaning and wide application of SBSC. Entering into effective memorandum of understanding through sharing of ideas, sharing of licences and franchising agreement as well as sharing of technological insight and technical know-how is a key to success amongst major players of this industry.

A generic sustainability Balanced score card for the Tourism and hospitality sectors shall act as a building block and can be applied as an initial draft for developing customised BSC for every Tourism and hospitality organisation based on specific scenarios. The designed sustainability BSC aspires to facilitate the revival, sustenance and sustained growth of the Tourism and hospitality sector. The designed balanced scorecard also emphasised on the internal business process and the learning and growth perspectives where focus has been given on sharing of ideas where specially for Activities and attraction sharing of technical know-how and ideas as well as design is of extreme importance when the idea that has already been copyrighted by the provider of a particular amusement service shares it with another player in the hospitality industry in lieu of other technical services or financial emoluments. Similarly through continuous service can be provided to the customers through subscription-based models where food and beverages could be delivered to customers as a part of subscription model where a minimum subscription is paid at regular intervals to avail a wide array of service benefits which are exclusive in nature to the subscribers. As this industry is fragmented into 4 sub segments hence service of all these four segments could be provided as a part of the entire service ecosystem package at a reduced rate when available as a bundle of services by the customers. Cross subsidisation model can also be followed by tourism and hospitality industry whereby for example visitors who are residing in a particular hotel would get food and beverages at a subsidised or at a discounted rate as compared to other customers who might have come just for lunch or dinner without any intention of stay. Similarly the free model of service could also be provided by virtue of providing free pick up and drop from airport or nearest railway station to the hotel or place of accommodation. Owing to the diverse, transitional nature and high vulnerability of Tourism and hospitality industry to external threats more KPIs are needed to encompass all the strategic objectives even after integration of the overlaying KPI. The study hereby tries to prove the importance of sustainability balance scorecard in context of the dynamic tourism and hospitality industry with respect to the necessary key performance indicators.

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